

The Effect of Buteyko Complementer Technique on Recurrence Frequency in Patients Asthma Bronchiale

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Abstract

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory disorder and bronchial hypersensitivity to various allergen stimuli which is characterized by reversible narrowing of the airways and attacks in almost all types of ages both children and adults. The Buteyko breathing method tries to minimize alveolar ventilation in response to pulmonary hyperventilation, resulting in smooth oxygenation and a decreased risk of hypoxia, hyperventilation, and apnea during sleep. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of Buteyko's supplementary approach on the recurrence of asthma in individuals with bronchial asthma. This is a legitimate experimental study using a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) design. The research population consisted of all asthma patients who worked in the Sokaraja Community Health Center's working region. Respondents were taken by random sampling technique. The number of sampel was 74 and randomly assignment into 37 treatment and 37 control groups. The instrument used to measure the frequency of asthma recurrence was the Asthma Control Test (ACT) questionnaire. Analysis of the data used is the Anova Repeated Measures Test. The result shows that there was a significant effect of Buteyko's complementary technique on the frequency of asthma recurrence in patients with Asthma Bronchiale with (p value = 0,000 is $< \alpha = 0.05$). Buteyko's complementary technique can reduce the frequency of recurrence of asthma in patients with Bronchial Asthma.

Keywords: *Asthma Bronchiale, Frequency of Asthma Recurrence, Buteyko Technique.*

INTRODUCTION

According to the Global Asthma Report (2014), the number of people with asthma in the world is around 334 million, while the number of sufferers in Asia is around 5% (16,700,000) of the population. According to Teresa (2012) and Menzies et al. (2020), the highest prevalence of asthma in Southeast Asia out of a total population of 1,968 million people, there are 11.4 million cases of asthma with an average prevalence of about 5.8%. Asthma is most common in Korea and Japan, especially in urban areas with high population density. The high number of deaths in Japan is caused by the morbidity of Asthma. This is due to delays in medical help, non-adherence to long-term therapy in the treatment of Asthma.

According to data from Riskesdas (2013), the prevalence of asthma in Indonesia is around 4.5% (873,329) of the total population of Indonesia as much as 248,818,100. The highest prevalence was in Central Sulawesi 7.8% (873,329), East Nusa Tenggara 7.3% (817,367), DI Yogyakarta 6.9%, (772,580) and Jakarta 5.2% (582,580), while In Lampung the prevalence of asthma is 1.6% (179,149) of the total population. The highest incidence of asthma was at the age of 25-34 years 5.7% and 35-44 years 5.6% with the highest prevalence in women 4.6% and 4.4% in men.

Reports from the Asthma and Allergy Foundation of America (2010), the highest incidence of Asthma usually affects children (7-10%), ie ages 5-14 years. While in adults, the incidence of asthma is smaller, which is about 3-5%. According to a study conducted by the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (2007), the incidence of asthma in the 18-34 year age group was 14%, while the >65 year age group decreased to 8.8%.

One of the methods developed to improve breathing in asthmatics is breathing techniques, which can be in the form of aerobic exercise, gymnastics, and breathing techniques such as Thai chi, Yoga, Mahatma, Buteyko and Pranayama (Cohen et al., 2019). According to Kerstjens et al. (2020) and Heaney et al. (2021), there is one complementary therapy to improve the breathing of asthma sufferers that is scientific and comprehensive, namely the Buteyko method, which was discovered and developed by Professor Konstantin Buteyko from Russia. The Buteyko breathing technique is a breathing technique that focuses on nasal breathing, breath holding and relaxation. Buteyko teaches Asthma patients to undergo a series of shallow and slow breathing exercises, and encourages breathing through the nose (Melhorn et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2021; Chipps et al., 2018).

The Buteyko breathing technique seeks to decrease alveolar ventilation in asthmatic patients in order to counteract pulmonary hyperventilation (Kornmann et al., 2020; Sumino et al., 2020; Fernandez et al., 2021). Additionally, the Buteyko breathing method assists in balancing the blood's carbon dioxide levels, resulting in smooth oxygenation, and

can help minimize the occurrence of hypoxia, hyperventilation, and sleep apnea in asthma patient. (Sullivan et al., 2019; Harrison et al., 2021; Virchow et al., 2019). The Buteyko breathing technique is easier to apply, because the exercises are carried out with simpler movements compared to other breathing exercises that are well known in Indonesia such as asthma and yoga. Providing regular Buteyko breathing technique exercises will improve the poor respiratory system in asthmatic patients so that they can help achieve controlled asthma levels (Kolb, 2009; Cotte et al., 2020; Akar et al., 2020; Matsunaga et al., 2019). Good control is expected to prevent exacerbations, normalize lung function, obtain good social activities and improve the patient's quality of life (Sundaru, 2009; Zaeh et al., 2022; Boonpiyathad et al., 2018).

According to McHugh's study et al. (2003), "Buteyko Breathing Technique for Asthma: An Effective Intervention," evaluated the effect of Buteyko Breathing Technique (BBT) on medication consumption in Asthma patients. As a consequence, no significant difference in FEV1 (forced expiratory volume in one second) was seen across the groups. For six months following the commencement of therapy, the BBT group demonstrated a 50% reduction in the usage of inhaled steroids and an 85% reduction in the use of 2-agonists. In the control group the use of inhaled steroids did not change and the use of 2-agonists showed a decrease of 37% from the start of the study. The decrease in the use of drugs indicates a decrease in the frequency of attacks that occur in respondents. The conclusion of the study of McHugh, et al is the Buteyko breathing technique is safe and effective for asthma management.

Prastyanto (2016) and Kosse et al. (2019) conducted research at Yogyakarta State University on the Effect of Buteyko Breathing Exercise on Peak Expiratory Flow (APE) in Asthma Patients. They discovered a significant effect of Buteyko Breathing Exercise on Peak Expiratory Flow with a p value 0.000 0.05. Peak Expiratory Flow increased by an average of 89.17 L/min following therapy with the Buteyko Breathing Exercise. A study conducted by Nurdiansyah (2013), showed a strong influence between Buteyko's breathing technique on reducing asthma symptoms (p value 0.00 and eta squared value 0.93). Melastuti (2015), Shankar et al. (2019), and Pelaia et al. (2019) discovered a difference in the control value of asthma symptoms before and after the Buteyko breathing method was used increasing from 20.35 to 21.29 and the significance (p value 0.00 < 0.05).

METHOD

This is a quantitative True Experimental study that employs a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) design. The goal of this study was to investigate the effect of the Buteyko Complementary approach on the incidence of asthma recurrence in patients with bronchial asthma in the Bnayumas Regency's Sokaraja Health Center Work Area. The sampling methodology used the two-block randomization method, in which the treatment group was assigned code A and the control group was assigned code B based on the 74 respondents' inclusion criteria. Additionally, the frequency of asthma recurrence was assessed in both groups. The treatment given to the treatment group was the Buteyko complementary technique gradually once a week and evaluated 3 times regarding the frequency of asthma recurrence in 12 weeks using the Asthma Control Test (ACT) instrument (Knihtila et al., 2018; Evaristo et al., 2020). The ACT instrument consists of 5 aspects that are used to assess Asthma symptoms (morning, afternoon and evening), the usefulness of rescue medication and the impact of Asthma on daily life by scoring: Asthma fully controlled (25), Asthma partially controlled (20-24) and Asthma is not controlled (< 19). Test the data analysis using the Repeated Measures Anova Test.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The sample for this study was randomly assigned to the treatment group, which included 37 respondents, and the control group, which included 37 respondents. The study's findings were as follows:

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents based on age and gender in the treatment group and control group

Characteristics of Respondents	Treatment Group		Control Group	
	f	%	f	%
Age (years):				
15-24	14	37.8	11	29.7
25-34	9	24.3	10	27.1
35-44	6	16.2	8	21.6
45-54	5	13.6	6	16.2
55-60	3	8.1	2	5.4
Gender:				
Man	8	21.6	10	27.1
Woman	29	78.4	27	72.9
n (sample)	37	100	37	100

Source: data proceed

According to the chart above, the majority of respondents in the treatment group, 14 persons (37.8 percent), were in their late teens (15-24 years), whereas as many as 11 people were in the control group (29.7 percent). And the majority of responses in both groups are female.

Research by Saily (2014), the results showed that the largest frequency of research subjects according to age was the 45-54 year age group as many as 29 people (39.73%). The greatest frequency of research subjects according to gender was women as many as 57 people (78.08%). And the greatest frequency of research subjects according to the degree of asthma is moderate persistent as many as 35 people (47.94%). Another study by Pangestuti, et al. (2015) there is a decrease in respiratory function in terms of the Forced Expiratory Volume in one second w(FEV₁) value which has a significant relationship with age. From ages 35 to 40 years, the average FEV₁ decrease was 25–30 ml/year and those over 70 years experienced a total decline of 60 ml/year.

Table 2. The mean score of the frequency of asthma recurrence before and after the Buteyko complementary technique in the treatment group and the control group

Measurement Variable	Treatment Group			Control Group		
	Mean	SD	p value	Mean	SD	p value
Beginning of ACT	11.135	4.1242	0.000	9.378	2.4421	0.165
ACT 1	18.108	4.1284		9.514	1.9094	
ACT 2	23.919	1.8163		9.838	1.7875	
n (sample)	37			37		

Source: data proceed

According to the table above, the mean ACT score and standard deviation in the treatment group changed significantly at the start of ACT, ACT 1, and ACT 2, with a p value of 0.000 = 0.05, indicating that there was a significant mean score for the frequency of asthma recurrence in the treatment group before and after the addition of the complementary Buteyko technique. The p value of 0.165 was greater than 0.05 in the control group, indicating that there was no significant mean score for the frequency of asthma recurrence in the control group.

This is in accordance with the results of Freitas et al. (2021) and Hekking et al. (2018), showing a decrease in complaints of shortness of breath felt by respondents (decreased breathing frequency) and an increase in oxygen saturation and control pause in each exercise. So, it was concluded that the Buteyko breathing technique and mint leaf aromatherapy were effective in reducing the symptoms of shortness of breath and decreasing respiratory rate and increasing oxygen saturation in asthma sufferers.

Sutrisna's (2018) research indicates that the Buteyko breathing technique has a substantial influence on ACT, with a significance level of p 0.05. After receiving the Buteyko breathing method, the mean difference between ACT scores was much greater (19.79±1.47) and ACT scores at week III (17.50±1.78), week II (12.64±1.82), week I (9.57±1.95), and pretest (7.64±1.82). Post hoc analysis found that the fourth week post test (19.79 ± 1.47) was significantly better than the third week post test (17.50 ± 1.78), second week (12.64 ± 1.82), week I (9.57±1.95), and pre-test (7.64±1.82) in improving asthma control.

Another study by Cottini et al. (2020), that Buteyko breathing exercise affects the increase in oxygen saturation values of asthmatic patients and it is recommended to apply breathing exercises as a non-pharmacological method to increase oxygen saturation values with a significance value of 0.000. Research by Melastuti and Husna (2015), showed the average (mean) of asthma control increased from 20.35 to 21.29 with a significant value (p value 0.00 < 0.05). The conclusion of this study is that there are differences in asthma control before and after the Buteyko breathing technique.

Table 3. Post Hoc Test in the Treatment Group and Control Group

Measurement Variable	Treatment Group			Control Group		
	Mean diff	CI 95%	p value	Mean diff	CI 95%	p value
Beginning of ACT vs ACT 1	6.973	5.23-8.72	0.000	0.135	0.54-0.81	0.293
Beginning of ACT vs ACT 2	12.784	11.24-14.34	0.000	0.459	0.22-1.14	0.209
ACT 1 vs ACT 2	5.811	4.47-7.15	0.000	0.324	0.11-0.76	0.209
n (sample)	37			37		

Source: data proceed

According to the table above, the difference in the mean ACT score between the treatment groups occurred in each measurement, and the highest score was obtained in the initial ACT vs. ACT 2 measurement, which was 12.784 with a p value of 0.000 = 0.05, indicating that there was a significant difference in the mean of the measurements. In the therapy

group, the original ACT, ACT 1, and ACT 2 were used. According to the table above, the mean difference in ACT values in the control group for each measurement with the initial p value of ACT vs ACT 1 ($p = 0.293$), initial ACT vs ACT 2 ($p = 0.209$), and ACT 1 vs ACT 2 ($p = 0.209$) is greater than or equal to 0.05, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean of the measurements in the control group.

The findings of this study corroborate Maulani's (2014) research, which shown a decrease in the incidence of recurrence in asthmatic patients following Buteyko breathing exercises. Another study by van Bulow et al. (2018) and Togias et al. (2019), showed a strong influence between the Buteyko breathing technique on reducing asthma symptoms in asthmatic patients (p value 0.00 and eta squared value 0.93).

Table 4. Test the Difference in Results in Each Measurement in the Treatment Group

Measurement variable	Treatment Group (Mean and SD)	Control Group (Mean and SD)	Difference (CI 95%)	p value
Beginning of ACT	11.135 (4.1242)	9.378 (2.4421)	1.757 (0.186-3.328)	0.029
ACT 1	18.108 (4.1284)	9.514 (1.9094)	8.595 (7.104-10.085)	0.000
ACT 2	23.919 (1.8163)	9.838 (9.838)	14.081 (13.246-14916)	0.000
n (sample)	37			

Source: data proceed

According to the table above, the p values for each measurement in the treatment group and control group are at the beginning of ACT ($p = 0.029$), ACT 1 ($p = 0.000$), and ACT 2 ($p = 0.000$), indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the complementary technique of Buteyko has a significant effect on the frequency of asthma recurrence in the treatment group and control group.

Table 5. Test the difference in results in each measurement in the control group

Measurement Variable	Treatment Group (Mean and SD)	Control Group (Mean and SD)	Difference (CI 95%)	p value
Beginning of ACT	11.135 (4.1242)	9.378 (2.4421)	1.757 (0.186-3.328)	0.000
ACT 1	18.108 (4.1284)	9.514 (1.9094)	8.595 (7.104-10.085)	
ACT 2	23.919 (1.8163)	9.838 (9.838)	14.081 (13.246-14916)	
n (sample)	37			

Source: Data Proceed

According to the table above, the p value for the treatment group and control group combined in the three measurements is $p = 0.000 = 0.05$, indicating that the hypothesis is accepted and that Buteyko's complementary technique has a significant effect on the frequency of asthma recurrence in the treatment group and control group.

This is consistent with Bachir's (2017) research, which discovered a difference in the average frequency of asthma recurrence in patients with bronchial asthma with a value of $p = 0.020 = 0.05$, indicating that Buteyko's breathing technique had an effect on the frequency of bronchial asthma recurrence. According to Dupler cit Bachir (2017), the Buteyko breathing technique utilizes basic natural breathing techniques and is useful for reducing symptoms and improving severity in asthmatics.

Kartikasari (2019) found a significant difference in mean peak expiratory current (APE) between the intervention group (mean 126.4322.05 L/min) and the control group (mean 52.1456.45 L/min). There was a significant difference in the mean difference in recurrence frequency between the intervention group (mean 1.29 0.61) and the control group (mean 0.79 0.57) with a p value of 0.038, and there was a significant difference in the mean difference in recurrence frequency between the intervention group (mean 1.29 0.61) and the control group (mean 0.79 0.57). Diaphragmatic breathing exercises are considered in the management of asthmatic patients.

CONCLUSION

Based on the examination of the study discussion data, it can be stated that Buteyko's complimentary approach had a substantial influence on the incidence of asthma recurrence in patients with Asthma Bronchiale with (p value = 0.000 is $< \alpha = 0.05$). Buteyko's complementary technique can reduce the frequency of recurrence of asthma in patients with bronchial asthma.

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